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<https://doi.org/10.61796/ejheaa.v1i6.649>**THE RELATIONSHIP OF INTERPERSONAL COMMUNICATION BETWEEN PARENTS OF STUDENTS AND CHILDREN'S COGNITIVE DEVELOPMENT IN EARLY CHILDHOOD EDUCATION (PAUD) PERMATA HATI BUMI AGUNG WAY KANAN****Jupri, Iis Purnasari**

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Abstract:The problem in this research is the low cognitive development of class A students at PAUD Permata Hati Bumi Agung Way Kanan Regency. Aims to determine the relationship between interpersonal communication between parents and children with the cognitive development of class A students at PAUD Permata Hati Bumi Agung Way Kanan Regency. The research method in this research is correlational with the type of research used, namely quantitative research. The population in this study was 17 students. The sampling technique in this study used the Saturated Sampling Technique, where all the population in this study was sampled. The sample in this study included parents and children or in one class or study group, namely 34 people consisting of 17 children and 17 parents. The data collection technique used a questionnaire. The data analysis technique uses product moment correlation. The results of the research show that there is a significant relationship between interpersonal communication between parents and children and the cognitive development of class A children at PAUD Permata Hati Bumi Agung Way Kanan Regency.

Keywords:Interpersonal Communication, Cognitive Development.

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INTRODUCTION

Education plays an important role in expanding knowledge and shaping students' values and perspectives. School is a place where students can improve their abilities and explore the potential that exists within them. It is important for everyone to have access to quality education, as it opens up opportunities for individual development and the progress of society as a whole. With a good education, students can develop a deep understanding of themselves, the environment, and the world around them.

Through school education, individuals strive to improve their quality of life. There is a close relationship between a person's learning process and their participation in community activities. If a person makes progress in learning, then his life also tends to progress in reverse. teaching is first received through the family. From an early age, parents teach positive values to their children and tell them what is right and prevent them from doing bad and negative things. (Damayanti 2021)

Family is an environment that plays an important role for someone to grow, develop, and gain an understanding of the values that shape their character from now on. The learning process takes place throughout an individual's life. Ahmadi explained that the family is a place of meaningful dialogue between family members and is the initial meeting of which children become members. The family is also the main place for children to interact with everyday life. According to Indra Amarudin Setiana, the family is the first environment where individuals gain benefits, strength from sibling relationships, and develop character in everyday life which are interrelated, and can create relationships between individuals and society. (Indra Amarudin 2019).

Communication is two-way, where the communicator and the communicant exchange information, knowledge and experience. (Rahman 2015: p. 9) Interpersonal communication is the process of sending and receiving messages between two people or between a small group of people, with several effects and some immediate feedback. (Devito Maulana 2011) Meanwhile, according to Ngalimun, interpersonal communication is communication between individuals and is personal in nature, whether it occurs directly (without a medium) or indirectly (through a medium). (Ngalimun 2018) Supported by Another opinion according to Khodijah is that Interpersonal communication is communication done by someone with others, in which there is an influencing-influencing process between two parties and it takes place dynamically. (Khodijah, ., And . 2018). The meaning of this statement is that interpersonal communication is communication carried out by someone with another person, where there is a process that influences two parties and takes place dynamically. Humans will not find a good life without communication with each other, as well as communication with family, for example communication between parents and children. If there is good interpersonal communication between parents and children, there will be a similarity in meaning, so that the message of wishes conveyed by parents to their children is easy for the children to accept.

The preschool period is an important period where parents play a role in shaping and developing a child's personality. During this period, parents can instill positive tendencies in children, such as teaching them to speak politely, say thank you and sorry, ask permission before playing outside, or behave politely. In childhood, children begin to explore more general things and are influenced by the school environment or peers. Munisa Salma Rozana realizes that the role of parents is very important in guiding children. Apart from that, children are also influenced by the school environment and peers (peer groups). Parents can also see how children respond when faced with problems and this reflects the unique characteristics of the child's personality. Children's mentality and behavior is a reflection of their personality which develops over time. (Salma Rozana, Nurhalima Tambunan 2019).

Children's cognitive development involves the ability to think consistently, think symbolically, and solve problems. According to Piaget's theory, there are four stages of cognitive development in children, namely the sensorimotor stage, pre-operational stage, concrete operational stage, and formal operational stage. (Erma Susilawati Dewi DKK 2021: p. 12) Each of these stages shows important cognitive progress, starting from sensory and motor understanding to the ability to think abstractly and logically. Understanding these stages helps educators and parents support children's cognitive growth according to their developmental stages.

The process of cognitive development is a cycle that occurs in the central nervous system when a person thinks and develops progressively according to actual changes and stimuli in the

environment. One of the strongest theories in understanding cognitive development is Piaget's theory. Cognitive development focuses on thinking skills, including learning, critical thinking, forgiveness, and remembering.

Increasing cognitive abilities is directly related to improving various abilities, including communication, problem solving, social interaction, and adaptability. (Basri 2018) Overall, a person's cognitive abilities will continue to develop from birth through the child's interaction with his environment. During childhood, cognitive growth is very rapid, where children are able to quickly absorb and remember information that is relevant to them. Overall cognitive construction will influence children's self-confidence, with the self-exploration phase which can influence their perception of the surrounding reality at that time. (Basri 2018: p. 2-3)

According to Rifa'I, quoted in Nuning Setyowati, learning outcomes are changes in behavior that students receive after experiencing learning activities. Changes in behavior as a result of natural learning are quite broadly understood, covering the areas of knowledge (cognitive), attitudes (effectiveness) and skills (psychomotor) of students. The social environment can have a positive and negative influence on students. Socialization with peers or the social environment will be an important role for students. If students hang out with friends who are studious and smart, of course they will be motivated to be more active. On the other hand, if students hang out with students who are less diligent and less serious about learning, then you will be carried away by your friend's behavior like that. Things like this can be negative factors that cause problems for students in learning.

Apart from that, a harmonious family, where father and mother interact with each other lovingly and there is always family togetherness, will provide an environment that is conducive to the cognitive and intellectual formation of children. (Khadijah 2016) As stated by Shannon and Weaver, interaction is forms of human communication that influence each other, both intentionally and unintentionally. It is not only limited to communication using verbal language, but also involves expressions, images, skills, and innovation. Through communication, parents can understand their children's behavior and personality, and vice versa, children can understand what their parents expect. Because interpersonal communication patterns form a bond between parents and children, the better and more frequent the communication is, the deeper and more positive the interpersonal bond will be, where parents have control over the child through the advice given within the family. This means that parenting patterns are committed to the child's growth, bearing in mind that variations in parenting patterns can also influence the growth of each child. The many different parenting patterns will have an impact on the child's level of mental development, and vice versa, if the parenting patterns are not good then the child's mental growth opportunities will also be hampered.

METHODS

This research uses a quantitative approach with a correlational type. The aim of correlational research is to see the reciprocal relationship between two or more variables, find out how big the relationship is between one variable and another variable and obtain mathematical certainty whether the relationship between two or more variables is significant or not. The data collection technique in this research is a questionnaire and documentation technique. Data analysis carried out in this research

is; correlation test for variable triangulation technique. Triangulation is also defined as the activity of checking data through various sources, various techniques/methods, and various times.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

RESEARCH RESULT

1. Variable X Data (Interpersonal Communication)

Based on the results of research conducted by Dipaud Gem Hati Bumi Agung Way Kan, the distribution of answer choices and conversion of answer choices regarding interpersonal communication was obtained as follows:

Table 1.1

Distribution of Respondents' Answers about interpersonal communication

No Res	Angket																	Jumlah
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	
1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	11
2	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	13
3	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	12
4	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	13
5	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	11
6	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	9
7	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	11
8	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	10
9	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	12
10	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	10
11	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	9
12	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	12
13	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	11
14	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	13
15	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	10
16	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	10
17	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	12
jumlah	10	11	14	11	13	12	8	10	10	10	14	12	11	12	12	9	10	189
rata-rata	1	1	1	0,6	0,8	0,7	0,5	0,6	0,6	0,58	0,8	0,7	0,6	0,7	0,7	0,5	0,6	
rata-rata ind	0,68		0,7			0,606					0,685				0,55		3,221	

Based on the table above, it can be depicted in the form of a circle diagram as follows:

Picture of a circle diagram of respondents' answers about interpersonal communication at the Gem Hati Bumi Agung Way Kanan preschool

From the table above, it can be seen that the items that have the highest weight value regarding interpersonal communication are items number 3 and 11 with a total of 14 and an average value of

0.82, namely children are able and brave to express their opinions to others and children feel more active and connected when Learn to use the media around you. Meanwhile, the lowest weight score among the questionnaires above is number 7 with a total of 8 and an average score of 0.5, meaning that many children always ask their parents about what they see around them.

From the table above, it can be seen that the indicator that has the highest weight value regarding interpersonal communication is indicator number 4 with an average value of 0.7, namely the Empathy indicator. Meanwhile, the lowest weight value among the indicators above is number 5 with an average value of 0.606, namely the Supportive Attitude indicator. Based on the results, the overall average regarding interpersonal communication is 3.221. So it is concluded that there is poor interpersonal communication.

2. Variable Data Y (Cognitive Development)

Based on the results of research conducted at the Gem Hati Bumi Agung Way Kanan preschool, the assessment of cognitive development refers to the results of teacher assessments/documents. The distribution of answer choices and conversion of answer choices regarding AUD's cognitive development is as follows:

Table 1.2
Distribution of Respondents' Answers regarding cognitive development at
Preschool Gem Hati Bumi Agung Way Kan

No Res	Dokumen																		Jumlah
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	
1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	13
2	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	11
3	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	13
4	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	11
5	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	13
6	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	12
7	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	13
8	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	11
9	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	12
10	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	12
11	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	12
12	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	13
13	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	12
14	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	13
15	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	13
16	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	12
17	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	12
Jumlah	14	12	10	10	9	11	12	12	11	10	12	12	13	11	13	13	11	12	208
Rata-rata	1	0.7	0.6	0.6	0.5	0.6	0.8	0.8	0.6	0.6	0.8	0.82	0.8	0.64	0.8	0.8	0.6	0.82	
rata-rata Ind					0.685					0.715				0.73					2.13

Based on the table above, it can be depicted in the form of a circle diagram as follows:

Image of a circle diagram of respondents' answers regarding cognitive development at the Gem Hati Bumi Agung Way Kanan preschool

From the table above, it can be seen that the item with the highest weight value regarding cognitive development is item number 1 and the average value is 1, namely many people answered that children always put objects/items in their proper place/return to their original place. Meanwhile, the lowest weight score among the questionnaires above is number 5 with an average score of 0.52, that is, many people answered that children show curiosity about everything they see around them.

From the table above, it can be seen that the average indicator that has the highest weighted value regarding cognitive development is indicator number 3 with an average value of 0.73, namely the indicator of recognizing the concept of numbers, number symbols and letters. Meanwhile, the lowest weight value among the indicators above is number 1 with an average value of 0.685, namely the indicator of knowing general knowledge and science.

It can be concluded from all the research results in the distribution table of interpersonal communication and cognitive development of AUD, that sharing information, discussing certain topics, and sharing experiences from parents to children can help in the cognitive development of AUD in a better direction.

The table above shows the student X and Y questionnaire scores and their percentages, which with these percentages also shows that there is a relationship between variable Bumi Agung Way Right.

DATA PROCESSING**Correlation Test of Variable X with Variable Y**

$$r_{xy} = \frac{n \sum X_i Y_i - (\sum X_i)(\sum Y_i)}{\sqrt{(n \sum X_i^2 - (\sum X_i)^2)(n \sum Y_i^2 - (\sum Y_i)^2)}}$$

Dengan:

- r_{xy} : Angka indeks korelasi *Product Moment*
- n : Jumlah peserta tes/angket
- $\sum X_i$: Jumlah skor butir soal angket/tes
- $\sum Y_i$: Jumlah skor total
- $\sum X_i Y_i$: Jumlah hasil perkalian butir soal tes/angket

$$r_{xy} = \frac{n \sum X_i Y_i - (\sum X_i)(\sum Y_i)}{\sqrt{(n \sum X_i^2 - (\sum X_i)^2)(n \sum Y_i^2 - (\sum Y_i)^2)}}$$

$$r_{xy} = \frac{34.2312 - (189)(208)}{\sqrt{(34.2079 - (189)^2)(34.2704 - (208)^2)}}$$

$$r_{xy} = \frac{78608 - 39312}{\sqrt{(70686 - 35721)(91936 - 43264)}}$$

$$r_{xy} = \frac{39296}{\sqrt{(34965)(48672)}} = \frac{39296}{\sqrt{1701816}}$$

$$r_{xy} = \frac{39296}{41253}$$

$$r_{xy} = 0,952$$

Table 1.3
Helper Table for Calculating the Correlation of X with Y

No	X	Y	X ²	Y ²	XY
1	11	13	121	169	143
2	13	11	143	143	143
3	12	13	132	169	156
4	13	11	143	143	143
5	11	13	121	169	143
6	9	12	99	156	108
7	11	13	121	169	143
8	10	11	110	143	110
9	12	12	132	156	144
10	10	12	110	156	120
11	9	12	99	156	108
12	12	13	132	169	156
13	11	12	121	156	132
14	13	13	143	169	169
15	10	13	110	169	130
16	10	12	110	156	120
17	12	12	132	156	144
Amount	189	208	2079	2704	2312

Based on the results of rxy calculations using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation formula, the value of rxy = 0.952. The value of rcount is compared with the value of rtable($\alpha=0.05$; CI=95%; n=17) namely 0.482, the value obtained is rcount > rtable.

Significant Relationship Test (t test)

According to Sugiyono, "To test the significance of the relationship, namely whether the relationship found applies to the entire population, it is necessary to test its significance." Formula for the significance of Product Moment Correlation. Obtained a t value of 6.402. The tcount value is then compared with the ttable price for a 5% error in the two-party test and dk=n-2=17-2=15, then we get ttable = 2.042. It is known that tcount > ttable, namely 6.402 > 2.042.

Regression Analysis

According to Sugiyono, "The analysis can be continued by calculating the regression equation." The regression equation can be used to predict how high the value of the dependent variable will be if the value of the independent variable is changed." Regression analysis can be done with the formula:

$$\hat{Y} = a + bX$$

Where:

$\hat{Y}$ = Predicted value
a = constant

b = Regression

coefficient
X = Value of
variable X

To find out the regression constant (a) and direction coefficient (b), the formula proposed by Sudjana is used:

$$a = \frac{(\sum Y)(\sum X^2) - (\sum X)(\sum XY)}{n(\sum X^2) - (\sum X)^2}$$

$$b = \frac{n(\sum XY) - (\sum X)(\sum Y)}{n(\sum X^2) - (\sum X)^2}$$

Table 1.4. Helper Table for Calculating the Values of a and b

No	X	Y	X ²	Y ²	XY
1	11	13	121	169	143
2	13	11	143	143	143
3	12	13	132	169	156
4	13	11	143	143	143
5	11	13	121	169	143
6	9	12	99	156	108
7	11	13	121	169	143
8	10	11	110	143	110
9	12	12	132	156	144
10	10	12	110	156	120

No	X	Y	X ²	Y ²	XY
11	9	12	99	156	108
12	12	13	132	169	156
13	11	12	121	156	132
14	13	13	143	169	169
15	10	13	110	169	130
16	10	12	110	156	120
17	12	12	132	156	144
Amount	189	208	2079	2704	2312

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \frac{(\sum Y)(\sum X) - (\sum X^2)(\sum Y)}{(\sum X^2) - (\sum X)^2} \\
 &= \frac{(208)(2079) - (189)(2312)}{17(2079) - (189)^2} \\
 &= \frac{(432432) - (436968)}{(35343) - (35721)} \\
 &= \frac{-393725}{-378} \\
 &= 1.041
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \frac{(\sum Y) - (\sum X)(\sum Y)}{(\sum X^2) - (\sum X)^2} \\
 &= \frac{17(2312) - (189)(208)}{17(2079) - (189)^2} \\
 &= \frac{(39304) - (39312)}{(35343) - (35721)} \\
 &= \frac{-8}{-378} \\
 &= 0.02
 \end{aligned}$$

So that the values a and b are obtained as below:

To find out the regression equation for Y on X, use the formula:

$$\hat{Y} = a + bX$$

By entering the values obtained from the calculations above, a simple regression equation is obtained, namely:

$$\hat{Y} = 1.041 + 0.02X$$

This regression equation shows that in a constant state = 1.041, for every addition of variable

Coefficient of Determination Test (r²)

According to Sugiyono "Correlation analysis can be continued by calculating the coefficient of determination, by squaring the coefficient found." From this opinion, the coefficient of determination (r²) can be calculated using the formula:

$$\begin{aligned}
 r^2 &= (r_{xy})^2 \\
 &= (0.952)^2 \\
 &= 0.906
 \end{aligned}$$

Furthermore, according to Sugiyon, "From the coefficient of determination test, the

percentage of effectiveness of X over Y can be calculated by multiplying the value of r^2 by 100% ($r^2 \times 100\%$)."

Determinant Coefficient

$$KD = r^2 \times 100\%$$

Information:

KD = coefficient value determinant

r = correlation coefficient value

$$\begin{aligned} K.D &= r^2 \times 100\% \\ &= 0.906 \times 100\% \\ &= 90.6\% \end{aligned}$$

F Value Testing

To find out the value F calculate using the formula proposed by Sudjana, namely Variance Analysis for Simple Regression.

Table 1.6. Helper Table for Calculating the Value of $\sum(Y - \hat{Y})^2$

No	X	Y	$\hat{Y}$	$(Y - \hat{Y})$	$(Y - \hat{Y})^2$
1	11	13	1,261	11,739	137.8
2	13	11	1,301	9,699	94.07
3	12	13	1,281	11,719	137.33
4	13	11	1,301	9,699	94.07
5	11	13	1,261	11,739	137.8
6	9	12	1,221	10,779	116.18
7	11	13	1,261	11,739	137.8
8	10	11	1,241	9,759	95.23
9	12	12	1,281	10,719	114.89
10	10	12	1,241	10,759	115.75
11	9	12	1,221	10,779	116.18
12	12	13	1,281	11,719	137.33
13	11	12	1,261	10,739	115.32
14	13	13	1,301	11,699	136.86
15	10	13	1,241	11,759	138.27
16	10	12	1,241	10,759	115.75
17	12	12	1,281	10,719	114.89
Amount	189	208	21.47	186,523	2055.5
			7		2

Table 1.7. Data pair Y Repetition of X

No	X	K	N	Y	Y ²	$\sum y^2$	$\sum y$	$(\sum Y)^2$	$\frac{(\sum Y)^2}{n}$	JK ϵ
1	13	1	3	13	169	481	37	1,442	480.6	0.4
2	13			11	143					
3	13			13	169					
4	12	2	4	11	143	637	49	2,546	636.5	0.5
5	12			13	169					
6	12			12	156					
7	12			13	169					
8	11	3	4	11	143	611	47	2,443	610.75	0.25
9	11			12	156					
10	11			12	156					
11	11			12	156					
12	10	4	4	13	169	663	51	2,651	662.75	0.25
13	10			12	156					
14	10			13	169					
15	10			13	169					
16	9	5	2	12	156	312	24	623	311.5	0.5
17	9			12	156					
AMOUNT										1.9

Based on table 4.7. It can be seen that the data for variable X and variable Y are obtained in 5 groups, meaning that the value of $(nk) = 17-5 = 12$.

$$JK(ET) = 1.9$$

$$JK(Tc) = JK(res) - JK(ET)$$

$$= 2055.52 - 1.9$$

$$= 2053.52$$

$$S^2_{TC} = \frac{0}{-2}$$

$$= \frac{2053.52}{17 - 2}$$

$$= \frac{2053.52}{15}$$

$$= 136.90$$

$$S^2_e = \frac{0}{-}$$

$$= \frac{1.9}{17 - 5}$$

$$= \frac{1.9}{12}$$

$$= 0.158$$

DISCUSSION

Based on the results of research conducted on Permata Hati Bumi Agung Way Kanan Dipaud Children, the discussion of the research results is as follows:

From the distribution of the results of parents' answers and observations regarding interpersonal communication between parents and children, it is known that the cognitive development of children at the Gem Hati Bumi Agung Way Kanan preschool is increasing. There are 13 aspects that must be considered in interpersonal communication, including: 1) Honesty about the problems faced by children and parents. 2) There is honesty regarding what children want or express to their parents in the form of communication. 3) There is an open attitude between children and parents so that there are no wrong opinions or perceptions between each other. 4) Able to feel and understand what the child feels towards other people or children. 5) Have a sense of caring about what the child feels. 6) Being able to understand other people's opinions shows empathy. 7) Able to provide support in the form of guidance and direction from parents for children. 8) Able to provide positive responses to children. 9) Provide opportunities to develop yourself and make decisions. 10) Able to be a good listener. 11) Show positive feelings and thoughts. 12) Able to put yourself in the same position as other people. 13) Able to create equal/equal conditions. With this interpersonal communication, AUD's cognitive development has a positive and significant relationship which is shown by students with their attitudes, including: 1) recognizing objects based on function (knives for cutting, pencils for writing. 2) Using objects as symbolic play (chairs). as a car). 3) Recognize the cause and effect symptoms related to him. 4) Get to know simple concepts in everyday life (drizzle, rain, darkness, light, light, etc.). 5) Create something according to your own ideas. 6) Classify objects based on shape or color or size. 7) Classify objects into the same group or similar groups or paired groups with 2 variations. 8) Get to know AB-AB and ABC-ABC patterns. 9) Sort objects by 5 according to size or color. 10) Know the concept of much and little. 11) Counting the number of objects one to ten. 12) Get to know the concept of numbers. 13) Recognize number symbols. 14) Recognize letter symbols.

From the analysis requirements test, namely testing whether there is a positive relationship between variable X and variable Y, obtained from the value $r = 0.952$. compared with the r_{table} value for an error of 5% and confidence interval (IK) = $100\% - 5\% = 95\%$ and for $n = 17$, namely 0.482. Obtained a comparison of $r_{count} > r_{table}$, namely $0.952 > 0.482$. Thus it is known that there is a positive relationship Between variable

From the analysis requirements test, namely testing whether there is a significant relationship between variable The comparison obtained between $t_{count} > t_{table}$, namely $6.402 > 2.042$. Thus it is known that there is a significant relationship between variable

From regression testing obtained: a) Regression equation $\hat{Y} = 1041 + 0.02X$. This regression equation shows that in a constant state of 1041, for every time there is interpersonal communication between parents of students, the cognitive development of AUD will increase by 0.02 from interpersonal communication. b)

From the coefficient of determination test, the value of $r^2 = 0.906$ is obtained. From the determination value (r^2) the percentage of Communication Relationships can be seen

Interpersonal Between Parents of Students and Cognitive Development of Children in Permata Hati Bumi Agung Way Kanan is 90.6%.

From the F test, the value obtained from the variance analysis list above is obtained by the F value calculated = 2.96 and this value is greater than Ftable with dk in the numerator $k=17$ and dk in the denominator = $n-2 = 17-2 = 15$, namely 2.21. Thus $F_{count} \geq F_{table}$ is $2.96 > 2.21$, so H_0 which states there is no relationship is rejected and H_a which states there is a relationship is accepted. Thus, it can be seen that the research hypothesis proposed by the author is accepted, namely that there is a positive and significant relationship between interpersonal communication between parents of students and the cognitive development of children in Permata Hati Bumi Agung Way Kanan.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on research results and discussion of the relationship between interpersonal communication between parents and students and the development of children's cognitive development at Paud Permata Hati Bumi Agung Way Kanan. It can be concluded that there is a positive and significant relationship between interpersonal communication between parents of students and the cognitive development of children at Paud Permata Hati Bumi Agung Way Kanan. The magnitude of the interpersonal communication relationship between parents of students and the cognitive development of children at the Permata Hati Bumi Agung Way Kanan Preschool can be categorized as "Strong".

Based on the conclusions above, this research, the researcher provides suggestions to future researchers, hopefully it can be used as a reference for other researchers to develop the same research but with different research subjects.

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